

COAGULATION STUDIES OF THE LATEX OF *CRYPTOSTEGIA GRANDIFLORA*, R. Br. A WAR TIME SOURCE OF VEGETABLE RUBBER.
PART II. EFFECT OF COAGULANTS ON THE
QUALITY OF RUBBER

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A sample of latex has been coagulated with various coagulants. The coagula after extraction with alcohol, alcoholic potassium hydroxide and alcoholic hydrochloric acid have been analysed for proteins and ash. The observations show that the quality of rubber in general is not affected by a coagulant and 1/5 of resins, 1/7 of proteins and 1/9 of inorganic constituents originally present in latex remain adsorbed on rubber. An explanation of coagulation phenomena has been given.

The present investigation is the outcome of a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, p. 191) which embodied results of coagulation of the latex of *Cryptostegia grandiflora* achieved by chemical (acids, alkalis, salts) and miscellaneous reagents, water, heat, electric current, mechanical stirring, auto-creaming and spontaneous or auto-coagulation and advanced some conclusions but reserved explanation about coagulation for a future report.

The present communication adduces arguments about the phenomena of coagulation and also describes the effects and changes produced in rubber when it is obtained by coagulating the latex with various coagulants.

A sample of latex on coagulation with coagulants gave percentages of dry rubber content (D.R.C.) ranging from 9.2-10.8, total solids, 18.4 and the serum solubles etc. as 7.6. The coagula were analysed for ash, total nitrogen, resins and rubber. They were next extracted with alcoholic potassium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid and in the unextracted residues ash and nitrogen were again estimated. It was found that the coagula did not show any further appreciable loss of resins, proteins and inorganic constituents after acid and alkali treatment. It was also evident from observations that the composition of rubber except in coagula obtained by auto-coagulation and cream (water) was more or less uniform and did not vary with the coagulants. Detailed examination of resins extracted from rubber is in progress and will form part of a separate communication.

The latex of *Cryptostegia grandiflora* is a milky white emulsion of minute globules suspended in an aqueous serum of complex composition while coagulation is a process of de-emulsification and resolution of latex into a coagulum and serum by agencies which may be physical and chemical in nature. The coagulum formed by the fusion of rubber with resins, proteins, and inorganic constituents has a spongy mesh work and is filled with serum but after its removal on pressing acquires a tough, tenacious and elastic structure. It has not been possible to obtain a coagulum consisting of pure rubber hydrocarbon by coagulants described in this investigation.

Number of theories have been advanced at times to explain the phenomena of coagulation. One postulates the phenomena to be due to the removal of protein (Weber, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3108; Flamant, *Caoutchouc et la Guttapercha*, 1912, 9, 6135; Hauser, 'Latex', New York, p. 91) or resin films (de Jong and Tromp-de Hass, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 3293). Coagulation is

* Only the ash and nitrogen determinations in this investigation have been done in collaboration with M. L. Mathur,

attributed by some to the action of enzymes (O de Vries, *India Rubber World*, 1924, 70, 729) or bacterial activity (Corbet, *Bull. No. 1. Rubber Res. Inst., Malaya*; Rhodés and Sekar, *J. Rubber Res. Inst. Malaya*, 1934, 5, 176; Eaton and Grantham, *Agric. Bull. F. M. S.*, 1915-1916, IV, 26; Gorter and Swart, *Meded. Rubber Proefst., West Java*, 1916, 6; de Vries, *Archief*, 1924, 8, 233); while Gardner considers it a purely physical phenomenon caused by disturbance of the physical equilibrium of the latex (*Caoutchouc et la Gutta percha*, 1905, 2, 351) and according to Kruyt (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1922, 100, 250) latex is a lyophilic colloid of feeble solvation whose stability can be modified by electric charge and the solvation. "The particles of rubber carry a negative charge and if this be neutralised by the addition of acid or metallic ions, the solvation alone would be insufficient to assure stability of the system. In the same way, if in a latex of lightly charged particles the feeble solvation is nevertheless sufficient to produce stability, coagulation will result if the solvation be reduced by addition of dehydrating agent, e.g. alcohol or a conc. solution of caustic alkali." ("The Chemistry and Technology of Rubber Latex" by C. F. Flint, 1938, p. 114).

Our own observations show that coagulation of the latex of *Cryptostegia grandiflora* is brought about (i) by agents which coagulate proteins and which neutralise the charge on rubber particles, (ii) by hydration (water) and dehydration (anhydrous sodium sulphate, potassium carbonate, caustic alkali and alcohol), (iii) by auto-coagulation (enzymes and bacterial activity), (iv) by shaking, centrifuging, when the p_H remains unaltered, (v) by smoking, heat, electric current, etc.

The data further show that the rubber particles carry a negative charge and resins and proteins are not completely removed from the rubber but a portion remains adsorbed on it while another is eliminated during the process and is probably of a different nature. These observations lead us to share the views expressed by Kruyt and we think that coagulation is brought about on account of profound changes produced by physical and chemical agencies which destroy the stability of the system by partial or complete elimination of resins, proteins and serum constituents, neutralisation of charge on rubber and its separation as coagulum and by the disruption of electrical, molecular and cohesive forces that pervade latex of *Cryptostegia grandiflora*. We visualise a molecule of latex to be composed of a central core of rubber which is suspended in a stout bag of resins filled with serum and this bag is further enclosed in another bag made of proteinous matter, the intervening space being filled with serum. Internal changes due to enzymes etc. or the external to chemical or physical agencies make a puncture in the bags when the serum oozes out while the sac walls collapse and fuse with rubber. These fused particles on account of their lightness tend to rise to the surface of serum to form a dense layer of cream and it is by further fusion and coalescence of these cream particles that a spongy coagulum is produced during coagulation. Failure of coagulation or stabilisation of latex under certain conditions or at certain periods of its metabolism is probably due to an increase in tone and resistance of the films associated with rubber and the concentration of coagulants is not enough to overcome their protective action.

EXPERIMENTAL

A sample of latex obtained in the month of October, 1943, from Oakhla (Delhi) plantations having p_H , 4.6 was coagulated with various coagulants shown in Table I. For each coagulation 50 c.c. latex were taken and a coagulum was immediately obtained when alcohol, acetone, water, steam, sodium hydroxide were used as coagulants but with picric, acetic and mineral

acids and salt solutions the latex after mixing with the coagulant was kept overnight when it thickened and on warming and stirring with a glass rod for 2-10 minutes the flocks separated which soon coalesced together to a spongy white coagulum. The coagulum in each case after pressing and washing with water was kept dipped under water for two days. It was next kept in boiling water for half an hour. All the coagula were dried in an air-oven at 90°. When coagulation was effected with pyridine, alcohol and sodium hydroxide two volumes of latex were used. One coagulum from pyridine and sodium hydroxide was washed with water alone and the other was dipped in acetic acid (10%) before washing and they are shown in Table I as "pyridine (water), pyridine (acid), sodium hydroxide (water), sodium hydroxide (acid)". From alcohol coagulation one coagulum was removed at once from the serum while the other was allowed to remain in it overnight and they are shown in the table as 'alcohol I and alcohol II'. The serum had in some cases turbidity and from that of alcohol was analysed for nitrogen when it gave a value of 10.47 % (65.63 % as protein). Besides, one coagulum was obtained by centrifuging and another by spontaneous or auto-coagulation while the whole latex was secured by completely drying the latex to a constant weight at 90°. The total solids of one experiment are shown as cream (water) and for obtaining them latex (50 c.c.) was diluted with water (200 c.c.) when flocks separated which after removing from serum were dried at 90°.

TABLE I

% D. R. C. obtained by coagulating latex with various coagulants

No.	Name of coagulant.	Coagulant in c.c. or g.	Dilution with water.	Serum.	μ n	% D. R. C. on vol. basis.
1	Alcohol I	50 c.c.	...	Brownish with suspension	4.6	9.22
2	Alcohol II	50 c.c.	...	" " "	4.6	10.07
3	Acetone	50 c.c.	...	" " "	4.6	10.86
4	Picric acid	0.05 g.	5 c.c.	Yellow and turbid	...	10.34
5	Pyridine (water)	0.025 c.c.	"	Slightly dark and turbid	5.0	10.50
6	Pyridine (acid)	0.025 c.c.	"	" " "	5.0	10.31
7	Sodium hydroxide (water)	N-soln.	"	" " "	...	10.23
8	Sodium hydroxide (acid)	"	"	" " "	...	9.77
9	Acetic acid	0.25% soln.	"	" " "	4.2	10.37
10	Sulphuric acid	0.1% "	"	" " "	4.2	10.19
11	Nitric acid	0.1% "	"	" " "	4.2	10.27
12	Hydrochloric acid	0.25% "	"	" " "	4.2	10.36
13	Sodium chloride	0.05% "	"	" " "	4.5	9.83
14	Ammonium sulphate	" "	"	" " "	4.4	10.25
15	Alum (potash)	" "	"	Brownish and turbid	4.5	10.62
16	Calcium chloride	" "	"	" " "	4.4	10.42
17	Aluminium sulphate	" "	"	Slightly dark and turbid	4.4	10.44
18	Pot. sulphate (anhd.)	5 g.	"	" " "	4.5	10.43
19	Water (to complete coagulation).	...	...	Clear, straw coloured	...	9.80
20	Steam (till 130 c.c. condensed)	...	...	...	...	10.11
21	Cream (water)	...	200 c.c.	Straw coloured	...	10.20
22	Centrifuge (till coagulum separated).	...	...	Turbid	...	10.60
23	Auto-coagulation	...	...	Straw coloured	4.2	10.80
24	Whole latex	...	...	...	...	18.36*

* Total solids are on the weight of latex.

TABLE II
Composition of coagula

No.	Coagula from	Percentage composition of coagula.					Percentage composition of coagula. on latex					Percentage of substances removed with serum	
		Ash	Nitro- gen	Pro- tein	Resins	Rubber	Moisture	Ash	Nitro- gen	Pro- tein.	Resins		Rubber
1	Alcohol I	0.73	0.59	3.69	13.52	82.06	81.64	0.07*	0.05	0.34	1.25	7.57	9.14
2	Alcohol II	0.84	0.69	4.29	13.37	81.50	81.64	0.08	0.08	0.43	1.35	8.21	8.29
3	Acetone	1.19	0.52	3.25	13.93	81.63	81.64	0.12	0.05	0.35	1.41	8.86	7.62
4	Picric acid	0.39	0.72	4.49	15.52	79.60	81.64	0.04	0.07	0.46	1.60	8.23	8.02
5	Pyridine (water)	0.39	0.68	4.23	14.29	81.09	81.64	0.04	0.07	0.44	1.50	8.51	8.61
6	Pyridine (acid)	0.14	0.68	4.26	13.40	82.28	81.64	0.01	0.07	0.44	1.38	8.47	8.05
7	Sodium hydroxide (water)	1.30	0.35	2.21	15.14	81.35	81.64	0.13	0.04	0.23	1.55	8.32	8.13
8	Sodium hydroxide (acid)	0.44	0.40	2.28	14.66	82.62	81.64	0.04	0.04	0.22	1.43	8.07	8.52
9	Acetic acid	0.25	0.58	3.64	13.39	82.72	81.64	0.03	0.06	0.38	1.39	8.57	8.00
10	Sulphuric acid	0.22	0.74	4.60	13.66	81.52	81.64	0.02	0.08	0.47	1.39	8.30	8.18
11	Nitric acid	0.18	0.64	4.01	13.99	81.82	81.64	0.02	0.07	0.41	1.44	8.39	8.10
12	Hydrochloric acid	0.35	0.76	4.74	14.12	80.79	81.64	0.04	0.08	0.49	1.46	8.29	8.08
13	Sodium chloride	0.30	0.55	3.45	13.55	82.70	81.64	0.03	0.06	0.40	1.33	8.13	8.53
14	Ammonium sulphate	0.71	0.65	4.04	12.59	82.66	81.64	0.07	0.07	0.41	1.29	8.47	8.11
15	Alum (Potash)	0.33	0.61	3.79	12.79	83.09	81.64	0.03	0.06	0.40	1.38	8.81	7.76
16	Calcium chloride	0.32	0.54	3.39	15.10	81.19	81.64	0.03	0.06	0.35	1.57	8.46	7.94
17	Aluminium sulphate	0.68	0.78	4.79	14.62	79.91	81.64	0.07	0.08	0.50	1.93	8.34	7.93
18	Sodium sulphate (anhydrous)	0.69	0.74	4.60	15.70	79.01	81.64	0.07	0.08	0.48	1.64	8.24	7.93
19	Water	0.30	0.60	3.72	14.19	81.79	81.64	0.03	0.06	0.37	1.39	8.04	8.55
20	Steam	0.52	0.77	4.77	13.55	81.16	81.64	0.05	0.08	0.48	1.37	8.20	8.26
21	Cream (water)	0.81	1.24	7.74	18.28	73.17	81.64	0.08	0.13	0.79	1.86	7.46	8.16
22	Centrifuge	1.16	0.78	4.90	14.20	79.75	81.64	0.13	0.09	0.53	1.55	8.68	7.47
23	Auto-coagulation	0.56	1.34	8.34	17.74	73.36	81.64	0.06	0.14	0.90	1.92	7.92	7.56
24	Whole latex *	3.55	2.12	13.26	36.31	46.88	81.64	0.65	0.29	2.43	6.67	8.61	...

The results given in Table I confirm our previous findings and show that there is not much of difference in the percentages of coagula obtained by coagulating the latex with various coagulants. They range between 9.2-10.8 thus showing a slight variation of 1.6% part of which may be due to sampling as it is difficult to maintain the uniformity of the sample. The total solids amount to 18.4% and the serum solubles or otherwise give a figure of 7.6%

* Moisture has been assumed on the basis of loss suffered by latex on drying at 90°.

Under circumstances when the maximum difference in the percentages of coagula is 1·6 the water coagulation method seems to be the best as it does not require chemicals or keeping the latex overnight. The only difficulty of the process is that big coagulating pans would be necessary and to overcome this we think that cemented tanks of suitable size, depending upon the daily supply of latex with an exit at the bottom would serve the purpose.

In order to find out the quality of rubber the coagula were analysed for ash, nitrogen and resins and rubber was calculated by difference. Table II embodies the results and percentage composition of coagula on the basis of D. R. C. and latex. Their ash was determined by heating them slowly and carefully in a platinum dish. Catching fire of combustible products was avoided. The material charred and finally a white ash was obtained. The nitrogen was determined by the method of Kjeldahl and to obtain a value for protein the percentage was multiplied by the factor 6·25. For the determination of resins coagula (not less than 1 g.) were extracted with alcohol four times (25 c. c. each time) on a water-bath for 20 hours. The alcoholic extract of coagula except that of whole latex and cream (water) was concentrated and on keeping at room temperature deposited a white substance, showing nitrogen 0·916 (5·73% as protein). The filtrate from this substance on removal of the solvent gave an ether-soluble oily residue (3·2516 g.) showing a nitrogen content of 0·485% while the ether-insoluble fraction was further resolved into water-soluble (0·0524 g.) having nitrogen 0·895% and water-insoluble (0·1 g.) with 1·964% nitrogen.

The foregoing table shows a high percentage of ash in coagula obtained from alcohol, acetone, sodium hydroxide, alum, ammonium and sodium sulphates and still higher in cream (water), centrifuge, auto-coagulation and whole latex but less in coagula from acid coagulants or those which were dipped in acid solutions before washing. Thus the ash content of total solids (whole latex) is 3·56% (0·66% on latex) while those of other coagula depend upon a coagulant. No generalisation can be made except that by coagulation ash-free rubber is not possible and that greater portion of the inorganic constituents is removed by serum and washing. Total nitrogen on the weight of whole latex is 2·12% (13·26% when calculated as proteins and 0·39% as nitrogen and 2·12% as protein on the weight of latex). Coagula from auto-coagulation and cream (water) show nitrogen 1·335 and 1·230% (8·34, 7·74% as protein) respectively and these values are higher than those obtained for other coagula which range from 0·35-0·77% (2·2-4·8% as protein). From the data it is evident that part of nitrogen is serum-soluble (14·9% as protein) and partly insoluble (8·3% as protein) and removal of a portion (3·5-6·1% as protein) from this depends upon coagulants. Turbidity of the serum in some cases and the analytical results of turbid mass obtained from serum after coagulating the latex with alcohol further supports this view point. The observed value for nitrogen was 10·47% (65·6% as protein). However, all the nitrogen cannot be proteinous and a considerable portion of it contained in the latex is removed during coagulation but 3-4% in spite of washings go into the mesh work structure of the coagula and probably continue to form shells surrounding the rubber particles. Comparative vulcanisation studies of whole latex and of coagula produced by auto-coagulation, water, acids, alkalis will decide the role of proteins in rubber.

The whole latex shows 36·31% alcohol solubles (resins) (6·7% on latex) while total solids from cream (water) and coagulum from auto-coagulation give 18·3 and 17·7% respectively. In other coagula the alcohol solubles range between 12·6-15·7%. Thus more than half of the resins are serum soluble and seem to be different from those which remain adsorbed on rubber by the formation of protective films which are not

removed at p_H 4'6-4'2. Rubber has been calculated by difference. The table further shows that in the total solids of *Cryptostegia grandiflora* resins, proteins and inorganic constituents which remain adsorbed on rubber amount to 1/5, 1/7, 1/6 respectively of those originally present in the latex.

It appeared however, necessary to find out whether the rubber hydrocarbon of coagula would show any further variation of percentage on extraction with alcoholic potassium hydroxide and alcoholic hydrochloric acid solutions.

TABLE III

Distribution of ash and nitrogen in coagula and their losses on extraction with EtOH-KOH and EtOH-HCl solutions

Coagula from	Loss after alc. KOH extraction %	Loss after alc. HCl extraction %	N after alc. ex traction %	N after alc.KOH extran. %	N after alc.HCl extran. %	Ash after alc. extran %	Ach after alc.KOH extran. %	Ash after acl.KCl extractn %	Increa- se in ash after HCl extn. %
Group A. Alcohol I, II, acetone, pyridine (water.) (acid), sodium chloride, acetic, sulphuric, nitric, hydrochloric acids, ammonium sulphate and alum (potash).	1'14	0'64 inc.	0'47 (avg. of 12 samples)	0'60	0'62	0'64 (avg. of 12)	0'79	0'71	
No. Group B.									
1. Calcium chloride	2'04	0'39 inc.	0'54	Not det.	0'49	0'32	Not det.	0'57	0'25
2. Aluminium sulphate	0'81	0'42 inc.	0'78	"	0'82	0'68	"	0'91	0'23
3. Sodium sulphate	3'57	No loss	0'74	"	0'43	0'69	"	1'17	0'48
4. Picric acid	0'12	0'35 inc.	0'72	"	0'39	0'39	"	0'80	0'41
5. Sodium hydroxide (water)	1'64	0'33 inc.	0'36	"	0'43	1'30	"	1'25	—
6. Sodium hydroxide (acid)	0'07	0'23 dec.	0'40	"	0'32	0'44	"	0'76	0'32
7. Water	0'07	0'24 inc.	0'60	"	0'43	0'30	"	0'99	0'69
8. Steam	1'17	0'13 "	0'77	"	0'74	0'52	"	0'85	0'35
9. Cream (water)	2'32	2'34 "	1'24	"	0'67	0'81	"	1'26	0'45
10. Auto-coagulation	3'74	0'36 dec.	1'34	"	1'02	0'56	"	0'53	—
11. Whole latex	10'38	0'33 dec.	2'12	"	0'17	3'55	"	0'86	—

Extraction of the Coagula with Acoholic Potassium Hydroxide and Alcoholic Hydrochloric Acid Solutions.—The coagula were divided into two groups, A and B. The group A comprised 12 coagula while there were 11 in group B and were kept separate. The extraction was carried out with 0.5-N-alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (100 c.c. for group A and 25 c.c. for each of the coagula of group B) The solution was prepared by dissolving potassium hydroxide (30 g.) in water (30 c.c.) and diluting the solution with alcohol (1000 c.c.) on the water-bath for six hours. The coagula were washed with alcohol and finally with water (twice) by warming on the water-bath for 6 hours. They were dried at 90° in an air oven and then in *vacuo* over sulphuric acid. Nitrogen and ash were determined for the coagula of group A only and the coagula of both the groups were next extracted with 0.5% alcoholic hydrochloric acid for six hours (30 c.c. for each sample of group B and 150 c.c. for

group A.) The coagula were washed with alcohol and finally with water and were dried as in the previous case. There was no loss of any significance by this treatment. There was a slight increase or decrease in weight. The coagula after extraction with potassium hydroxide solution showed losses which were more in those obtained from cream, steam and auto-coagulation, while the whole latex showed a loss of 10.4 %. The losses are due to the elimination of inorganic matter and proteins etc. as supported by data in Table III. The ash and nitrogen were determined in all the coagula of group A and B after their extraction with alcoholic hydrochloric acid and they required more sulphuric acid for digestion than it was ordinarily required in Kjeldahl estimation for nitrogen.

The foregoing table shows the course of nitrogen and ash in coagula after various treatments. In some cases there is an increase in the ash content and this corresponds with their increase in weight after alcoholic acid extraction. It is possible that some potassium hydroxide remained in rubber and combined with hydrochloric acid and the resultant potassium chloride adsorbed on rubber.

C O N C L U S I O N S

1. Whatever coagulant is used for coagulation a certain proportion of inorganic constituents, proteins and resins (1/9, 1/7, 1/5 respectively) of those originally present in latex remains adsorbed on rubber.

2. Half of the total solids are eliminated with serum during coagulation.

3. The quality of rubber does not vary with a coagulant.

4. The molecules of latex are sac like bodies consisting of an inner core of rubber surrounded by protective films of resins and proteins and the intervening spaces are filled with serum constituents. A puncture in the latex sac expels the serum constituents and brings about a collapse of the protective films which get adsorbed on rubber and these fused sacs float in serum as cream. It is by further fusion of cream particles that a spongy coagulum of rubber is produced.

5. Coagulation is brought about on account of profound changes in latex produced by physical and chemical agencies which destroy the stability of the system by elimination of resins, proteins and serum constituents, by the neutralisation of charge on rubber and by the disruption of electrical, molecular and cohesive forces that pervade latex.

Ou thanks are due to Mr. J. P. Anderson, Controller of Rubber and Major H. R. Walden, Deputy Controller of Rubber for the facilities during this investigation.

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Received April 11, 1944.

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